

A STUDY TO EVALUATE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF PRANAYAMA ON ACADEMIC STRESS AMONG 1ST YEAR B.SC. (NURSING) STUDENTS AT SELECTED COLLEGES IN NELLORE, ANDHRAPRADESH"

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Abstract

Stress from many sources has been reported for some time by student nurse. The sources are like academic source, parental expectation, and competition for grade, relationship and career choice. Academic sources of stress like examination, long hours of study, assignments and grades, lack of free time, and lack of timely feedback after their performance, special elements of academic program like arrangement and conduction of workshops, also produce stress among student nurses. And also clinical sources of stress like while taking care of critically ill patients, interpersonal conflict with peer group, fear related to complete their clinical requirements, prolonged standing and performing catheterization, have also been associated with high level of stress. Nursing students have the same academic as other college students such as midterm and final examinations, research paper and other assignments. In additional, however nursing students also experience a clinical component which is highly stressful. Student often perform procedures that can cause serious harm to their patients and fear making a mistake. Students may face hostility or rejection from patients and their families. Additionally, students are in continuous contact with faculty and often believe that every task or interaction is being evaluated.

Need for study: It is obvious that stress is present among nursing students. Excessive stress can be harmful to student's academic performance. Additionally students who perceive their stress level as very high often will become depressed. Researchers at all India institute of medical sciences (2002) in New Delhi have discovered a clear link between rhythmic breathing process and a state of relaxed alertness and recommended the practice of Pranayama for breathing stress. Lindop (1999) identified conflict between the ideal and real clinical practice was also a source of stress. He also found that time management problems. When trying to complete nursing tasks added to a student's perception of stress. Stress is very common for the nursing students. Many relaxation techniques help to reduce the stress. Pranayama is one among the relaxation techniques. So the investigator felt the need for Pranayama to reduce stress among nursing students. **Objectives:** To assess the level of stress among 1st year nursing students selected college, To evaluate the effectiveness of Pranayama on stress, among 1 year nursing students, To associated the level of stress among 1st year nursing students with their selected socio demographic variables **Material and methods:** The data collection procedure carried out after obtaining Permission from the Institutional Ethics Committee, principal, Sree Narayana Nursing College, Nellore. Investigators visit each participant and introduced her and explained the nature and purpose of the study. Confidentiality of the information will be assured by taking informed consent from the participants 100 participants will be selected by using non probability convenience sampling technique who fulfilled the inclusion criteria. The data collected by administering the two parts of the tool. The investigator distributed the tool for filling the socio demographic data and the structured questionnaire which consists of various items related to among Dr.NTRUHS B.Sc. (N) students. Data collection procedure: The data collection procedure was done for a period of 1 week. After obtaining the permission, data collection will started. 40 samples would selected by using non probability convenience sampling technique. Dr.NTRUHS B.Sc. (N) students who fulfill the inclusion criteria would selected and the confidentiality of shared information will assured structured questionnaire will adopt to

collect the data, questionnaire will be given to I year B.Sc. (N) students and give 30 minutes to complete the **Result:** The data was analyzed by the frequency and percentage as per shown that Dr.NTRUHS B.Sc. (N) students were having Discusses the level of stress on effectiveness on Pranayama on academic stress among I year nursing students, at Moderate 19(19%) and Severe 81(81%). Mean and standard deviation, the mean value (pre test) is 59.49 and standard deviation is 7.71 (post test) mean value is 83.22 and standard deviation is 11.37. **Conclusion:** Pranayama technique is an effective intervention to reduce academic stress.

Keywords: Assess, Knowledge, Maternal and Child Health Scheme, I Year B.Sc. (N) Students.

BACKGROUND AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE PROBLEM

Stress from many sources has been reported for some time by student nurse .The sources are like academic source, parental expectation, and competition for grade, relationship and career choice. Academic sources of stress like examination, long hours of study, assignments and grades, lack of free time, and lack of timely feedback after their performance, special elements of academic program like arrangement and conduction of workshops, also produce stress among student nurses. And also clinical sources of stress like while taking care of critically ill patients, interpersonal conflict with peer group, fear related to complete their clinical requirements, prolonged standing and performing catheterization, have also been associated with high level of stress

Nursing students have the same academic as other college students such as midterm and final examinations, research paper and other assignments. In additional, however nursing students also experience a clinical component which is highly stressful. Student often perform procedures that can cause serious harm to their patients and fear making a mistake. Students may face hostility or rejection from patients and their families. Additionally, students are in continuous contact with faculty and often believe that every task or interaction is being evaluated.

One major source of stress of stress for nursing students are having various types of information to support critical thinking and decision making while learning the nursing role. So many relaxation techniques are there to reduce the level of stress. Pranayama is one of the relaxation techniques, in which mainly focus on the regulation of breathing pattern through which releasing the obstacles from energy field. This is very much useful to reduce the level of stress.

It is obvious that stress is present among nursing students. Excessive stress can be harmful to student's academic performance. Additionally students who perceive their stress level as very high often will become depressed.

Researchers at all India institute of medical sciences (2002) in New Delhi have discovered a clear link between rhythmic breathing process and a state of relaxed alertness and recommended the practice of Pranayama for breathing stress.

Lindop (1999) identified conflict between the ideal and real clinical practice was also a source of stress. He also found that time management problems. When trying to complete nursing tasks added to a student's perception of stress.

Stress is very common for the nursing students. Many relaxation techniques help to reduce the stress. Pranayama is one among the relaxation techniques. So the investigator felt the need for Pranayama to reduce stress among nursing students.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- To assess the level of stress among 1st year nursing students selected college
- To evaluate the effectiveness of Pranayama on stress, among 1st year nursing students.
- To associated the level of stress among 1st year nursing students with their selected socio demographic variables.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS

1. **Effectiveness:**-It refers to the significant reduction of stress level as determined by the difference between pre test and post test scores.
2. **Pranayama:**- Pranayama is the art of harmonizing breathing. It has the capacity of freeing mind from stress. Pranayama is the yogic practice means "vital life force and yama means to control. In yoga breath is associated with Pranayama
3. **Academic stress:**-Academic stress is defined as a constant state in which one is subjected to physical or mental pressure, tension or strain.
4. **1st year nursing students:**-Students who are studying B.sc nursing program.

Assumption:

- Well being of 1 year nursing students is ensured by the reduction of stress.
- All the 1st year nursing students will have some level of stress Pranayama can help to reduce the level of stress.

Hypothesis

H0:- The significant of study is not having the knowledge about Pranayama on academic stress among 1st year nursing students.

H1:- The significant of study may have the knowledge about Pranayama on academic stress among 1st year nursing students.

H2:- The significant of study may / may not have the knowledge about Pranayama on academic stress among 1st year nursing students.

Delimitations

- The study is limited to the age group of the subjects between years.
- Data collection period is limited to four weeks.
- The study is limited to nursing students who are studying in a selected nursing college.

Projected outcome

The findings of the study will help the student nurses to practice pranayama to reduce the stress.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research approach: Quantitative research approach

Research design: Pre-experimental one group pre-test and post-test design

Setting of the study: the study will be conducted at selected nursing colleges, Nellore.

Population:

Targeted population: All 1st year B.Sc. Nursing Students.

Accessible population: 1st year B.Sc. Nursing Students at selected nursing colleges, Nellore.

Sample: 1st year B.Sc. nursing students who fulfilled the inclusion criteria.

Sampling technique: Non probability convenience sampling technique.

Sample size: 100 1st year B.Sc. nursing students.

The estimated sample for the present study is calculated by using Yemem's formula
$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)}$$

Where n = sample size

N = total number of population = 100

e = desired level of precision = 0.05

$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$

$n = \frac{100}{1 + 100(0.05)^2}$

$100/1.25 = 80$ Hence n = 80

Considering 10% attrition, a sample of 8 is added to the estimated sample size. Hence, a total of samples size is 88. Considering the round figure 100 will be included for the present study.

Criteria for sample selection

Inclusion criteria: Nursing students who are between 17-19 years. Willing to participate in the study.

Exclusion criteria: Nursing students who are suffering from major illness. Already in practice of any stress reduction techniques

Variables

Independent variable: Pranayama technique

Dependent Variable: Academic stress

Demographic variables: It consist of age, religion, type of family, father's education, mother's education, father's occupation, mother's occupation, family income per month, medium of instruction of previous school education, academic performance in previous school education, number of siblings, residence, hobbies, any previous experience of stay in hostel.

Scoring interpretation

The level of stress will be measured in terms of stress scores. The total possible score was 120. Each item scored as Never-0, occasionally- 1, frequently – 2, Always – 3. Item No 34, 36, 37 had reversed scoring. For the purpose of the study, the level of stress was classified as

Total score	Severity of stress
<40	Mild Stress
41–80	Moderate Stress
81–120	Severe Stress

Validity

The validity of the tool will be obtained from three experts from nursing field.

Reliability

The reliability of the tool will be tested by split half method by using Karl Pearson's correlation coefficient.

$$r = \frac{2r}{1+r}$$

Feasibility

The feasibility of the study will be tested by conducting pilot study.

Ethical clearance

Ethical clearance certificate will be obtained from institutional ethical committee of College of Nursing, Nellore.

Consent

Written consent will be taken from parents and assent from the participants in College of Nursing, Nellore, before going to conduct the study.

Autonomy

All participants were considered to make rational decision and moral choice during the participation of study.

Justice

The study will be useful for B.Sc. nursing students in Narayana College of Nellore.

Beneficence

1st year B.Sc. nursing students would benefit from the study as training on coping strategies will be conducted after the study.

Non maleficence

The study would not be harmful to participants.

Confidentiality

All participants were assured that confidential information would not be shared with others and it is used only for the study purpose.

Veracity

Maintain trust relationship between the investigator & samples.

Pilot study

Pilot study will be conducted at selected nursing colleges, Nellore. Formal permission will be obtained from the concerned authority of nursing college. Pilot study will be conducted for one week period of time. The participants of 1st year B.Sc. nursing students will be selected by using non probability convenience sampling technique. A brief introduction about researcher will be explained.

Data collection procedure

Study will be conducted in given period of time. A sample of 100 will be selected by non probability convenience sampling technique considering the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Pre test will be conducted to assess the level of academic stress with the help of a Self administered questionnaire. Pranayama technique will be implemented. Total students will be divided in to two groups each group contains 50 students. Two sessions will be conducted in the morning and evening Consent will be taken from participants. Each participant will be taken 20-30 minutes to complete the questionnaire. Confidentiality of responses will be assured. The data will be coded, tabulated, and analyzed. Based on the experience and feasibility of the pilot study, the investigator will proceed to conduct the main study. Everyday participants will practice Pranayama in two sessions under the supervision of the researcher (morning and evening) for the duration of 30 minutes. Post test will be conducted with same questionnaire to assess the academic stress response with Pranayama technique.

PLAN FOR DATA ANALYSIS

The data will be analyzed in the terms of objective of pilot study using the descriptive statistics. The plan for data analysis as follows

Sl. No	Data Analysis	Method	Remarks
1.	Descriptive statistics	Frequency, Percentage distribution of Mean and Standard Deviation	Distribution based on socio demographic variables To determine the level of knowledge regarding complementary feeding practices among the mothers of infant in selected rural area Nellore
2.	Inferential Statistics	Chi-Square test	To find out the association between the level of knowledge regarding complementary feeding practices among the mothers of infant in selected rural area Nellore

Frequency and Percentage distribution based on their socio demographic variables among nursing students in selected colleges, Nellore.

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage distribution of students based on Age.
(N=100)

Age in years	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
17-18	53	53
19-20	40	40
21-22	7	7
Total	100	100

Table 1 Represents that, with regards to the Age of patients 53(53%) are below 18 years, 40(40%) are between 19-20 years, 7(7%) are between 21-22 years.

Fig 1: Percentage distributions of students based on age

Frequency and percentage distribution on based on their effectiveness of Pranayama on academic stress among 1st year nursing students at selected colleges Nellore.

Table 2: Frequency and Percentage distribution of effectiveness of Pranayama on academic stress among 1st year nursing students

Pre test

(N=100)

Level of Stress	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Mild	8	8
Moderate	92	92
Severe	-	-
Total	100	100

Table 2 Discusses the level of stress on effectiveness on Pranayama on academic stress among 1 year nursing students, at 8(8%) had mild, 92(92%) had moderate.

Fig 2: Percentage distribution of effectiveness of Pranayama on academic stress among 1st nursing students.

Frequency and percentage distribution on based on their effectiveness of Pranayama on academic stress among 1st year nursing students at selected colleges Nellore.

Table 3: Frequency and Percentage distribution of effectiveness of Pranayama on academic stress among I year nursing students

Post test (N=100)

Level of Stress	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Mild	-	-
Moderate	19	19
Severe	81	81
Total	100	100

Table 3 discusses the level of stress on effectiveness on Pranayama on academic stress among I year nursing students, at Moderate 19(19%) and Severe 81(81%).

Fig 3: Percentage distribution of effectiveness of Pranayama on academic stress among 1st year nursing students.

Table 4: Mean and standard deviation of pre test and post-test on effectiveness of Pranayama on academic stress among 1st nursing students at selected college, Nellore.

(n=100)

Criteria	Mean	SD	Z-Value	Remarks
Pre test	59.49	7.71	Cv=1.69	NS*
Post test	83.22	11.37	Tv=1.96 P= <0.005	

Table 4: shows that, mean and standard deviation, Z ratio of pre test and post-test of effectiveness of Pranayama on academic stress among I year nursing students. The pre test mean was 59.49, with SD 7.71. The post- test mean was 83.22 with an SD of 11.37.

The calculated Z Value (1.69) is less than the tabulated Z value (1.96) at 0.05 level of non significant.

DISCUSSION

The main aim of the study was to identify the effectiveness of Pranayama on academic stress among 1st year nursing students at selected colleges, Nellore.

The quantitative approach and experimental design was adopted for the study. The study was conducted in selected college in Nellore. The sample for the present study was 100 1st year nursing students. Non Probability simple random sampling technique was adopted to select the 1st year nursing students. Observational checklist was used to identify the effectiveness of Pranayama on academic stress ethics. Finally data was analyzed and interpreted by using descriptive and inferential statistical method and tabulated according to the objectives and hypothesis of the study.

Objectives

- To assess the level of stress among 1st year nursing students at selected college
- To evaluate the effectiveness of Pranayama on stress, among I year nursing students.
- To associated the level of stress among 1st year nursing students with their selected socio demographic variables.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

The results discussed based on the stated objectives as follows

Description of socio-demographic variables:

- Shows the frequency and percentage distribution of age, were 53(53%) belongs to 17-18 years, 40(40%) belongs to 19-20 years, 7(7%) belongs to 21-22 years.
- Shows the frequency and distribution of type of family were belong to 100(100%) Joint family.
- Refers to the frequency and distribution of fathers education were, 35(35%) belongs to primary and elementary, 65(65%) belongs to High school.
- Refers to the frequency and distribution of mothers education were,9(9%) belongs to Illiterate 66(66%) belongs to primary and elementary, 25(25%) belongs to High school.
- Shows the frequency and distribution of fathers occupation were, 12(12%) belongs to employed 47(47%) belongs to Unemployed and 41(41%) belongs to self employed.
- Shows the frequency and distribution of fathers occupation were, 26(26%) belongs to employed 55(55%) belongs to Unemployed and 19(19%) belongs to self employed.
- With regards to the frequency and distribution of Family income per month were, 62(62%) belongs to up to 5, 000, 33(33%) belongs to Rs, 5001-7500 and 5(5%) belongs to Rs, 7, 501-10, 000.
- With regards to the frequency and distribution of Medium of instruction of previous school education were, 73(73%) belongs to English, 20(20%) belongs to Tamil and 7(7%) belongs to Malayalam.

- In shows the frequency and distribution of Pattern of previous education were, 15(15%) belongs to State board 85(85%) belongs to Matriculation.
- With regards the frequency and distribution of Number of siblings were, 10(10%) belongs to No siblings, 48(48%) belongs to 1-2, 42(42%) belongs to 3 & above.
- In shows the frequency and distribution of Hobbies were, 35(35%) belongs to hearing the music and 65(65%) belongs to playing indoor games.
- In view of the frequency and distribution of Residence were, 43(43%) belongs to Hostel and 57(57%) belongs to days scholars.

Finding of the study based on objectives:

- To assess the level of stress among 1st year nursing students in selected college

Pre test:

The study shows with regards to the level of stress among I year nursing students 19(19%) had moderate and 81(81%) had severe stress. With regard to the study the mean score for the 1st year nursing students was 59.49 with the standard deviation of 7.71.

Post test:

The study shows with regards to the level of stress among I year nursing students 19(19%) had moderate and 81(81%) had severe stress. With regard to the study the mean score for the 1st year nursing students was 83.22 with the standard deviation of 11.37.

- To evaluate the effectiveness of Pranayama on stress, among I year nursing students.

The comparison of pre test and post test effectiveness of Pranayama on academic stress revealed that pre test mean of stress score 59.49 with SD 7.71. The post test mean of stress scores was 83.22 with SD of 11.37. The calculated value of 'z'-test was 1.69 and the table value was 1.96. The calculated value was less than the table value; hence the research hypothesis was accepted.

Study will be conducted in given period of time. A sample of 100 will be selected by non probability convenience sampling technique considering the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Pre test will be conducted to assess the level of academic stress with the help of a Self administered questionnaire. Pranayama technique will be implemented. Total students will be divided in to two groups each group contains 50 students. Two sessions will be conducted in the morning and evening Consent will be taken from participants. Each participant will be taken 20-30 minutes to complete the questionnaire. Confidentiality of responses will be assured. The data will be coded, tabulated, and analyzed. Based on the experience and feasibility of the pilot study, the investigator will proceed to conduct the main study. Every day participants will practice Pranayama in two sessions under the supervision of the researcher (morning and evening) for the duration of 30 minutes. Post test will be conducted with same questionnaire to assess the academic stress response with Pranayama technique.

- To associated the level of stress among 1st year nursing students with their selected socio demographic variables.

- In association to Age in years, calculated (x2) value is 0.128 and table value is 5.99. The calculated value is more than table value, so there is non significant association.
- In association to Type of family, calculated (x2) value is 0 and table value is 0. The calculated value is equal to table value, so there is significant association.
- In shows to the Father's Education, the calculated (x2) value is 1.577 and table value is 9.49. The calculated value is more than table value, so there is significant association.
- In shows to the Mother's Education, the calculated (x2) value is 2.53 and table value is 9.49. The calculated value is less than table value, so there is non significant association.
- In association to Father's Occupation, the calculated (x2) value is 0.3 and table value is 5.99. The calculated value is more than table value, so there is significant association.
- In association to Mother's Occupation, the calculated (x2) value is 0.432 and table value is 5.99. The calculated value is more than table value, so there is non significant association.
- With reference to Family Income per month the calculated (x2) value is 36.033 and table value is 7.82. The calculated value is more than table value, so there is non significant association.
- With reference to Medium of instruction of previous school education, the calculated (x2) value is 0.191 and table value is 7.82. The calculated value is less than table value, so there is significant association.
- With reference to pattern of previous education, the calculated (x2) value is 0.074 and table value is 7.82. The calculated value is less than table value, so there is significant association.
- In shows Number of Siblings, the calculated (x2) value is 0.631 and table value is 5.99. The calculated value is less than table value, so there is non significant association.
- With reference to Hobbies, the calculated (x2) value is 1.577 and table value is 9.49. The calculated value is more than table value, so there is non significant association.
- With reference to Residence, the calculated (x2) value is 31.094 and table value is 3.84. The calculated value is more than table value, so there is non significant association.

Summary, implementation, recommendation and conclusion

This chapter deals with the summary, conclusion and recommendations of the study. It also includes implications for nursing practice, nursing education and nursing administration for future research. The quantitative research approach was used for the study.

The samples were selected based on the sampling criteria. A total of 100 1st year nursing students were included in the study. Informed consent and the purposes of the study were explained. Data collection was conducted with the help of a checklist. The data was analyzed by using descriptive statistics (i.e. frequency and percentage distribution, mean and standard deviation) and inferential statistics.

Objectives

- To assess the level of stress among 1 year nursing students at selected college
- To evaluate the effectiveness of Pranayama on stress, among 1 year nursing students.
- To associated the level of stress among 1 year nursing students with their selected socio demographic variables.

Major findings of the study

- With regards to age in year, 53(53%) were between 17-18 years.
- With regards to Type of family, 100(100%) are joint family.
- In respect to Fathers education, 65(65%) were High school.
- In respect to Mothers education, 66(66%) were primary and elementary.
- In context to Fathers occupation, 47(47%) were unemployed.
- In context to Mothers occupation, 55(55%) were unemployed.
- In context to Family income per month, 61(61%) between up to 5, 000
- With regards the Medium of instruction of previous school education, 73(73%) were English.
- In respect to pattern of previous education, 85(85%) were matriculation.
- With regards to Number of siblings, 48(48%) between 1-2
- In view of any hobbies, 65(65%) were playing indoor games.
- In context of Residence, 57(57%) were Days scholars.

Result: In relation to association among 1 year nursing students shows that there is a significant association between practice on Pranayama ethics with their selected socio demographic variable such as age in year, Type of family, Fathers education, Fathers occupation, Mothers occupation, Family income per month, Hobbies and Residence.

There is Non-significance association between effectiveness of Pranayama on academic stress with their socio demographic variable like Mothers education, Medium of instruction of previous education, pattern of previous education and Number of siblings.

Implications for nursing practice There are several important implications for nursing practice.

Nursing service

- Pranayama technique can be introduced there as a stimulating mode of intervention by the nurses, for relieving the stress of the patients as well as the relatives.
- The nurses in the hospital set up also can arrange Pranayama sessions for the patients.
- The nurses working in service side to be taught to implement Pranayama to reduce the level of stress.

Nursing education

- It is important to have educational program on Pranayama for all nursing students.
- Nurses can make their own arrangement to use Pranayama can practice themselves.

Nursing administration

- The nurse administrator coordinates her work with the teaching aspect among nursing students by practicing and supervising Pranayama technique.
- Nursing administrator should organize in- service education program on Pranayama technique.

Nursing research

- Nursing research to be done to find out the various innovative methods to reduce stress.
- Research can be conducted on various populations at various settings

CONCLUSION

Pranayama technique is an effective intervention to reduce academic stress.

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